

Remediation technology of chlorpyrifos residue in red chillies planted on light-textured soils and heavy-textured soils

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ABSTRACT

The pests on chilli plantations area serious issue in considering to chillies. Pest can cause a serious failure to the chilli crop, therefore planting chillies is closely related to a high cost. The next action, the chilli farmers treat pests with excessive use of pesticides. Currently, a widely sold and used pesticide by chilli farmers in the field is a pesticide that has chlorpyrifos as its active ingredients. There are at least 40 brands of pesticides made from chlorpyrifos, and 8-10 of them are used by chilli farmers. The aim of research is to evaluate of chlorpyrifos residues remediation chilli planting soil with different textures. The research has been conducted at the greenhouse of the Agricultural Environment Research Institute (IAERI) during July-November 2017. The experiment was carried out in pots with soil media from Magelang (light texture) and Pati (heavy texture). The study used randomized block design with 3 replications, 2 factors and 5 treatments (10 treatment combinations). The two factors are soil texture, namely: (T1 = light texture and T2 = heavy texture). Meanwhile, the five treatments are: (P1) urea coated with activated charcoal; (P2) urea coated with activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia; (P3) urea coated with biochar; (P4) urea coated with biochar enriched with microbial consortia; (P5) farmers methods (150 kg/ha urea). The results showed that urea coated with biochar and urea coated with biochar enriched with microbial consortia effectively reduced the chlorpyrifos residue both in light textured soil from Magelang and heavy textured soil from Pati. The clay content in heavy textured soil from Pati increases the degradation process of chlorpyrifos in the soil. The results of chilli plant successively from the highest are urea coated with activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia > urea coated with charcoal > urea coated with activated charcoal > urea coated with biochar enriched with microbial consortia > farmers methods (in light textured soil from Magelang). While urea coated by activated charcoal > urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia > urea coated with activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia > farmers methods > urea coated with biochar (in heavy textured soil from Pati).

Keywords: *remediation, chlorpyrifos residue, soil texture, chilli plants*

INTRODUCTION

Red chilli is one of the most found vegetables in almost every household kitchen. The symptoms of a rise in the price of red chillies cause worries in the markets. It even forced the government to intervene to stabilize the price. Due to the sudden rise in the red chillies' price, inflation to other needs might also happen. National chilli needs 92,000 ton per year in 2016, and it increase from year to year.

Although the national of chilli production has met the needs, some efforts to increase its production must also be carried out, especially when there is a decreased production (during the rainy season). During that period, if the efforts to increase the production have done, the farmers would get a decent selling price and income profit. For this reason, a breakthrough in technological innovation to increase chilli production must be carried out to obtain a suitable level of production according to the level of need. The management of plant pest, the increasing of chilli population per unit area (from 20,000 plants/ha to 30,000 plants/ha), and the implementation of Good agriculture Practices (GAP) are expected to become efforts for increasing the production of red chillies.

The pest management in the vegetable sector including red chillies is inseparable from the use of chemical pesticides. This can be seen from the high use of pesticides among vegetable farmers, although at the same time field school of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and GAP have also been implemented by the government. Due to the product appearance and economic reasons, the use of pesticides in the management of IPM field school in the horticultural sub-sector remains high. In addition, there are no signs of declining use of pesticides in the field.

As a result, chlorpyrifos residues are easily detected in soil and vegetables. Harsanti et al. (2014) found chlorpyrifos residues in the shallots center production in Bantul. Chlorpyrifos residue of 0.0035-0.0112 mg/kg was found in shallots in Brebes (Poniman et al., 2017). Red chilli from Pogalan and Kapuan (Magelang Regency) was found to contain chlorpyrifos between 0.1616-0.1688 mg/kg (Poniman and Indratin, 2014). Karlina et al. (2014) found chlorpyrifos residues in red chillies in traditional and modern markets in Makassar, while Miskiyah and Munarso (2009) found chlorpyrifos residues in chillies from Bandungan even though they found small amounts (below the MRLs).

At least 95 brands of insecticides which contained chlorpyrifos can be found all over Indonesia (http://pestisida.id/simpes_app/rekap_kimia_formula.php), and those 8-10 brands were used by red chilli farmers to manage the pest. According to WHO (2009), chlorpyrifos which is known as contact poison and stomach poison, has a

II-level danger (dangerous). Based on that definition, it is seen as important to prevent the continuous effect of the use of chlorpyrifos.

In general, red chilli can be planted in every soil condition, texture, ecosystem, and rain precipitation. As long as the drainage system can be managed well, red chilli can be produced effectively. Red chilli that was planted in upland area usually has a light texture. On the other hand, red chilli that was planted in lowland area has heavy texture. Based on that difference, chlorpyrifos residue is expected to give different effect in different textures of soil. This study is aimed to evaluate of remediation technology of chlorpyrifos in red chilliplanted on light textured soil and heavy textured soil.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried conductedat a green houseof Agricultural Environment Research Institute(IAERI) during July-November 2017. The experiment was carried out in potswith soil media from the vegetable fields of Ngablak village, Magelangdistrict and the other one from Ngurensiti Village, Wedarijaksa sub-district, Pati district. The both location are Central Java Province. The study used randomized block design with 3 replications, 2 factors and 5 treatments (10 treatment combinations). These two factors are soil texture, namely: (T1 = light texture and T2 = heavy texture). Meanwhile, the five treatments are: (P1) urea coated by activated charcoal; (P2) urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia; (P3) urea coated by biochar; (P4) urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia; (P5) farmers methods (150 kg/ha urea).

The soil media taken from Magelang and Pati is air dried until it reaches absolute dryness and ready to be the planting media in the pots. The soil is weighed as much as 15 kg and put into a pot volume of 20 kg. The next step is added water to the ground surface, cover the top of the pot tightly, and stir every day for one week so that the chlorpyrifos residue carried by the soil media becomes homogeneous. After one week of opening the lid of the pots, keep stirring for a week so that the soil reaches a field capacity (ready for planting). A month old chilli seedlings were planted as many as 3 plants were planted in each pot, and gradually reduced at the age of 7 and 14 days (left with one truly healthy seed). The treatment application was carried out when the plants were 15 HST, as well as the basis for calculating the sampling time for chlorpyrifos residues. The application of fertilizers is still carried out according to the schedule of local farmers, whereas during planting the application of the active ingredient of chlorpyrifos pesticides should not be used.

In determining the residual chlorpyrifos insecticide, soil samples were taken at a depth of around 10 cm from the surface of each pot. During the study, soil samples were taken 4 times (before application of treatment, 1 Day

After Application (DAA), 40 DAA, and harvest). Soil samples were analysed in the integrated laboratory of the Agricultural Environment Research Institute (IAERI).

Laboratory analysis was carried out in the following steps: 10 g of soil samples which had been destroyed, each were put into Soxhlet paper tubes, extracted with 100 ml acetone solvent on the soxhlet base. Extraction is carried out for 6 hours at 80 ° C. After 6 hours, the extraction is evaporated until it is slightly dry in the evaporator at 45 ° C. The effluent obtained from the evaporation results was transferred into a 150 ml separating funnel with the help of 25 ml n-hexane solvent, then extracted with 25 ml acetonitrile solvent. The n-hexane layer is at the top while the acetonitrile layer is on the bottom.

The acetonitrile layer was evaporated/concentrated in the evaporator at 45°C, and then dissolved with n-hexane + acetone (ratio 9: 1) as much as 5 ml. Eluent was put in the test tube with the help of acetone solvent until it reaches the volume to 5 ml. From the solution, the content of chlorpyrifos residue was determined by gas chromatography (Ohsawa et al., 1985).

Gas chromatography was used by Shimadzu 2014 with SPL-1 injector, Flame Photometric Detector (FPD) detector, auto sampler AOC-201, injector temperature 2300C and detector temperature 2500C, inject volume 1 µL. Insecticide residues are calculated using formulas (PPI, 2006):

$$R = \frac{A_c}{A_s} \times C_s \times \frac{D_f}{S_w}$$

Information:

Ac = sample area

As = standard area

Vic = sample injection volume (µL)

Vis = standard injection volume (µL)

Ks = standard concentration (ppm)

B = initial volume (mg or ml)

Vfc = final volume (ml)

R = recovery (%)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the chemical and physical properties of the soil used as the media

The analysis of soil from Magelang showed that it has acidic pH (5.5), low organic C content (1.76%), moderate total N (0.32%), moderate total K₂O (22.8 mg/100g), and moderate P₂O₅ (38.4 mg/kg), with moderate CEC (18.6 me/100g), and sandy clay texture. This soil is categorized as light textured soil

with a composition of 48% clay, 35 sand, and 17% dust. Whereas, the soil from Pati has a rather acidic pH (5.84), high organic-C levels (4.65%), low total N (0.18%), moderate total K₂O (26.1 mg/100g), and high P₂O₅ (52.3 mg/kg), with moderate CEC (22.3 me/100g), as well as the texture of dust clay. This soil is categorized as heavy textured soil with a clay composition of 52%, 36% dust, and 12% sand.

Residual chlorpyrifos insecticide in soil samples and red chilli samples

The type and properties of soil such as the type of clay, and the content of soil organic matter can affect the accumulation of insecticide residues in the soil (Soejitno, 2006). Each time of observation shows significantly different (Table 1). The chlorpyrifos insecticide residue generally decreased at 1 DAA and again increased at the next observation even though it was still low compared to the initial value (before the application of treatment).

Tabel 1. Chlorpyrifos insecticide residue in light-textured soil and heavy-textured soil which were planted by red chilli, Jakenan 2017

Treatment	DBA	Experiment time		
		1 DAA	40 DAA	Harvest
----- mg/kg -----				
T1P1	0.4200ab	0.0925cd	0.1699ab	0.2360b
T1P2	0.3781ab	0.0631d	0.1116b	0.2577b
T1P3	0.5500a	0.3648a	0.0978b	0.2650ab
T1P4	0.482ab	0.2457b	0.1893ab	0.2180bc
T1P5	0.4010ab	0.1977bc	0.3135a	0.3780a
T2P1	0.3065ab	0.0777cd	0.1269b	0.2900ab
T2P2	0.4351ab	0.1618bc	0.1603b	0.2673ab
T2P3	0.3069ab	0.1887bc	0.1117b	0.1133c
T2P4	0.5613a	0.2354bc	0.0704b	0.2177bc
T2P5	0.2769ab	0.1547c	0.1399b	0.2533b
KK (%)	14.67	16.34	13.87	17.23

The same number in the same column which was followed by the same letter showed not different and real BNT test 1%

Description : T1 = Light-textured soil, T2 = heavy-textured soil. P1 = urea coated by activated charcoal (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg/ha AA); P2 = urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia (120 kg ha urea: 30 kg/ha AA + consortic microbes); P3 = urea coated by biochar (120 kg ha urea: 30 kg/ha biochar); P4 = urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg ha biochar + microbial consortia); and P5 = farmers' methods. DBA =Day before application; DAA= Days after application)

Before the application of chlorpyrifos residue treatment ranged from 0.2769-0.5613 mg/kg, the combination of treatments showed significantly different. In the following observations (1 DAA), showed a decrease in all treatments namely to around 0.1547-0.3648 mg/kg between real different treatments. At the observation of 40 chlorpyrifos residues DAA became around 0.0704-0.3135 mg/kg, while at the time of harvest the chlorpyrifos residues ranged from 0.1133 to 0.3780 mg/kg.

The half-life of chlorpyrifos in the soil is around 60-120 days (Sahid, 1988), if the half-life has been reached and the amount of residue found increases it can be ascertained that magnification has occurred by a number of soil living creatures (Cassidy et al. 1996; Ardiwinata et al. 2005). Even though the pH value was not observed in this study, the increase in chlorpyrifos residue was estimated to be caused by an increase in soil pH. Soil pH can also affect the process of degradation of pesticide residues in the soil (Li et al., 2009). In many cases, increasing soil pH inhibits the degradation process of pesticides, at pH > 7.5 can cause low persistence of chlorpyrifos in the soil (Yucel et al. 1999), increasing pH due to wheat biochar decreases the absorption of Deuron herbicides (Yang et al., 2004), reduce herbicide Ametryne and Bromoxynil (Yang et al., 2004; Sheng et al, 2005).

The effect of biochar remediation material is consistent on both soil textures in reducing chlorpyrifos insecticide residues to 40 DAA observations, and increases observations at harvest. The use of biochar as ameliorant material has a positive impact on the soil environment, because biochar has high stability in the process of degradation and nutrient retention. The positive effects of biochar on improving soil properties make conditions stable (Warnock et al., 2007; Chan et al., 2007; 2008; Asai et al., 2009; Busscher et al., 2010; Sohi et al., 2010; Novak et al., 2010). The use of biochar can contribute to the uptake of the active ingredients of pesticides, reduce their mobility and reduce the risk of surface contamination and groundwater.

The ability of ameliorant material to reduce residue can be seen from the magnitude of the value of the initial residual decline (before the application of treatment) with the residual value at harvest (at the end of the plant period). Each ameliorant material has different abilities in degrading chlorpyrifos residues in the soil (Poniman and Indratin, 2014; Poniman, 2014). Ameliorant materials from organic materials from agricultural waste can reduce pesticide residues on agricultural land (Ardiwinata and Nursyamsi, 2012; Harsantiet al., 2010; Wahyuni, 2014; Poniman, 2014).

The treatment of urea coated with biochar and the treatment of urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia showed a high decrease compared to other treatments in both soil textures. The treatment of urea coated

bybiochar in light-textured soil can reduce chlorpyrifos residue by 51.82% and raise the decrease in value to 54.77% in the treatment of urea coated bybiocharenriched with microbial consortia. Meanwhile in heavy textured soil, both treatments reduced chlorpyrifos residue by 63.08% in urea coated bybiochar treatment and 61.22% in urea coated bybiochar enriched with microbial consortiatreatment.

Biochar is more effective in reducing chlorpyrifos residues in red chilli soil planted in different soil textures, compared to other treatments. However, it does not mean that other treatments cannot reduce the residual chlorpyrifos. The treatment of activated charcoal-coated urea fertilizer and consortia-enriched activated microbial coated charcoal can reduce residues by 43.81% and 31.84% respectively in light texture and by 5.38% and 38.57% in heavy textured soil. The magnitude of the reduction in chlorpyrifos residues in the soil during red chilli planting is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The decrease of chlorpyrifos residue in light textured soil and heavy textured soil during the red chilli cropping, Jakenan 2017

Treatment	Residues time			Decrease ---- % ----
	DBA	Harverst		
		----- mg/kg -----		
T1P1	0.4200	0.2360	0.1840	43.81
T1P2	0.3781	0.2577	0.1204	31.84
T1P3	0.5500	0.2650	0.2850	51.82
T1P4	0.4820	0.2180	0.2640	54.77
T1P5	0.4010	0.3780	0.0230	5.74
T2P1	0.3065	0.2900	0.0165	5.38
T2P2	0.4351	0.2673	0.1678	38.57
T2P3	0.3069	0.1133	0.1936	63.08
T2P4	0.5613	0.2177	0.3436	61.22
T2P5	0.2769	0.2533	0.0236	8.52

Description: T1 = Light textured soil, T2 = heavy textured soil. P1 = urea coated with activated charcoal (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg/ha AA); P2 = urea coated with activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortium (120 kg ha urea: 30 kg/ha AA + consortic microbes); P3 = urea coated with biochar (120 kg ha urea: 30 kg/ha biochar); P4 = urea coated with biochar enriched with microbial consortium (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg ha biochar + consorticmicrobes); and P5 = farmers' methods.

The biochar material is more effective in heavy textured soil than light textured soil. The heavy textured soil from Pati (clay-dust) has higher clay particles and is thought to facilitate absorption of chlorpyrifos residues. Yang et al. (2010) stated that the addition of biochar clay fraction could decrease the chlorpyrifos and fipronil. Sandy clay added with biochar from rubber wood can reduce carbofuran residues and chlorpyrifos. Clay content and soil characteristics determine the absorption of insecticides in the soil (Soejitno, 2006). Each insecticide compound has a functional group which can facilitate the absorption of residues by the soil. Soil and negatively charged clay easily absorb positive groups of insecticides (Rajagopal, et al, 1984).

In the product example (red chilli), there is no chlorpyrifos residue is found. However, it does not mean that it is free from chlorpyrifos residues, it may be that the amount of residue contained in chillies is not detected by GC with a detection limit of 0.0046 mg/kg. Chlorpyrifos residues can still be found in red chilli (Poniman et al. 2013; Poniman and Indratin, 2014; Miskiyah and Munarso, 2009)

The chilli weight was observed at 3 harvests (harvesting 1-3). The amount of chilli weight at each harvest is presented in Table 3. From the three harvests, chili yields were obtained between 174.35 - 214.41 g/plant. The chilli weight 3 times harvest showed a significant difference between the combinations of treatments. The application of layered urea showed better effectiveness on light textured soil than heavy textured soil, which indicated chilli weight on both soil textures.

The application of urea coated by activated charcoal and urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia showed stability of chilli yield in both soil textures, with better yields compared to other treatments. Activated charcoal as a coating is believed to increase the efficiency of urea fertilizer. Reported by Wahyuni et al. (2014) that urea coated with activated charcoal can increase yield and increase urea efficiency by up to 24%.

Although the coating of urea by biochar and biochar enriched with microbes did not show high results compared to the application of urea coated by activated charcoal and urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial, but not statistically significantly different. The addition of carbonaceous ameliorant materials besides being able to reduce chlorpyrifos residues can also improve secondary growth and increase crop productions (Glaser et al., 2002; Chan et al., 2007; Novak et al., 2009; Sohi et al., 2010; Busscher et al., 2010). Thus, remediation technology can be accepted as a new technology in order to increase crop productions.

Table 3. The chilli weights planted in pot systems with different soil textures, Jakenan 2017

Treatment	The chilli weight at...			Total (3 times harvest)
	Harvest-1	Harvest-2	Harvest-3	
----- g/plant -----				
T1P1	43.26bc	73.56b	84.58a	201.40
T1P2	53.81a	86.39ab	74.21b	214.41
T1P3	45.01b	75.92b	81.45ab	202.38
T1P4	30.61c	82.56ab	83.83ab	197.00
T1P5	31.57c	73.41b	69.37b	174.35
T2P1	36.13c	89.31a	86.39a	211.83
T2P2	47.32ab	82.34ab	74.34b	204.00
T2P3	37.31bc	69.89b	70.59b	177.79
T2P4	45.41ab	77.42ab	84.33a	207.16
T2P5	35.19c	70.21b	78.73ab	184.13
KK (%)	12.42	15.05	11.94	

Description: T1 = Light textured soil, T2 = heavy textured soil. P1 = urea coated with activated charcoal (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg / ha AA); P2 = urea coated with activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortium (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg/ha AA + consortic microbes); P3 = urea coated with biochar (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg/ha biochar); P4 = urea coated with biochar enriched with microbial consortium (120 kg/ha urea: 30 kg/ha biochar + consortic microbes); and P5 = farmers' methods.

CONCLUSIONS

Urea coated by biochar and urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial effectively reduced chlorpyrifos residue in light-textured soil from Magelang and heavy-textured soil from Pati. The clay content in heavy textured soil from Pati increases the degradation process of chlorpyrifos in the soil. The results of chilli successively from the highest are urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia > urea coated by activated charcoal > urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia > farmers' methods (in light-textured soil from Magelang), while urea coated by activated charcoal > urea coated by biochar enriched with microbial consortia > urea coated by activated charcoal enriched with microbial consortia > farmers' methods > urea coated by biochar (in heavy textured soil from Pati).

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